

Dr David Braimer

Mental health practitioner

Email. David.braimer@protonmail.com

Adress: Oslo-Norway

ISBN

**NORTHAMPTON UNIVERSITY
TOP UP MBA PROGRAMME
LONDON SCHOOL OF MARKETING
2017-2018**

STUDENT ID NUMBER: 17450917

**MBA Thesis
STRM044**

**Analysing the Impact of Technological
Innovation on Health Service Delivery: A
Case Study of NHS UK”**

Total words: 14 978

ABSTRACT

Technological innovation is one of the biggest blessings in health service sector by which the sector has to embrace today's advanced form of growth and innovation. This study tends to explore the impact of technological innovation in the health service delivery in NHS UK. NHS is the public health service provider of the UK that provides quality and free health care services to its citizen expect charges in some cases. The main objectives of this study are to analyse the technological innovations employed in in NHS, its features, its impacts on health service delivery along with findings ways to improve quality of health care.

In the study, both primary and secondary sources of data and information are collected. A literature review was conducted by including literature from 2000 AD and onwards. A conceptual framework has been developed basing on the literature review. Likewise, an online survey (questionnaire) was conducted among the 60 participants that include patients and staffs of NHS (31 service user and 29 service provider). The participants were selected the through the use non-probability purposive sampling method.

The major findings of the study depict that technological innovation has a positive impact on the health service delivery in NHS UK. The findings reveal that easy and fast diagnosis and treatment, enhanced quality and standard, improved efficiency and service, reduction in medical errors, better research and development, improved efficiency and better communication within and outside are the impacts that technological innovations. However, few of the negative impacts like a high cost for the service user and mistakes due to technical defects have been found in this study. Towards the end some of the recommendations are provided basing on the findings of the study.

Key Words: Technological Innovation, Health Service Delivery, NHS, UK

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I take this opportunity to express my gratitude to everyone who has to provide direct and indirect support in conducting this study. This piece of work has been completed only through their constant support, guidance, love and care, I want to thanks them all from the core of my heart and would be indebted to all of them throughout my life. Firstly and most importantly, I would like to endow my gratitude to my respected supervisor Asanthi kodituwakku who continuously guides and supervise me throughout this research study. She was my source of inspiration and path shower, and I am indebted to her throughout my life. Her constant support, guidance, motivation and contribution is beyond my word of appreciation.

Secondly, I would like to thank NHS UK and participants of the survey for providing valuable data and information that I needed in the course of this study. Their contribution is significantly appreciative. Equally, I want to thank the scholars, researchers whose views and works I have included in this study.

Last but not the least, my special thanks go to my families and friends who always supported and inspired me to perform better. Their constant love, support and motivation always inspire to move in the right direction. They have a valuable and special position in my life, without them my life is incomplete.

I would like to bestow this piece of work to my dear and respected mother and my late father. Their enormous love, care and support throughout my life couldn't be expressed in words. They have always been my source of inspiration, role model and path shower in my life. Everything I do, I owe to them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	1
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	2
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND	6
1.2 BACKGROUND OF THE RESEARCH ORGANIZATION	7
1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT	8
1.4 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY	8
1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH	9
1.6 RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES	9
1.7 RESEARCH QUESTION	10
1.8 STRUCTURE OF THE RESEARCH	10
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	12
2.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK	12
2.2 HEALTH CARE SERVICES IN UK	13
2.3 TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN HEALTH SECTOR AND NHS UK	14
2.4 CHALLENGES FOR TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN HEALTH SERVICE SECTOR	15
2.5 IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS ON HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY	17
2.6 WAYS TO IMPROVE HEALTH SERVICE QUALITY IN UK	19
2.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	20
CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	22
3.1 OVERVIEW	22
3.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY	22
3.3 RESEARCH APPROACH	23
3.4 RESEARCH TECHNIQUE	24
3.5 RESEARCH METHOD/DESIGN	25
3.6 RESEARCH STRATEGY	26
3.6.1 Experiments	27
3.6.2 Case study	27
3.6.3 Survey	27
3.7 DATA COLLECTION METHOD	28
3.7.1 Secondary Source of Data	28
3.7.2 Primary Source of Data	29
3.8 POPULATION SAMPLING	30
3.9 RESEARCH INSTRUMENT	31
3.10 DATA ANALYSIS	32
3.11 RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY	33
3.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION	34
3.13 RESEARCH LIMITATION AND ACCESSIBILITY ISSUES	35
CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS	36
4.1 PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS	36
4.1.1 Gender of the Participants	36
4.1.2 Age Group of the Participants	37
4.1.3 Background of the Participants	38
QUESTIONS TO THE NHS STAFFS	39
4.1.4 Working Year	39
4.1.5 Preference about technological innovations	40
4.1.6 Agreeableness about technological innovation's help to provide effective health service	42
4.1.7 Impacts of technological innovations on health service delivery	42
4.1.8 Challenges for technological innovations in health sector	43

QUESTIONS TO THE SERVICE USER	44
4.1.9 Rating of NHS health service delivery	44
4.1.10 Use of technological innovations in health service	45
4.1.11 Impact of technological innovations on health service delivery	46
4.1.12 Improving quality of health service	47
4.2 DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS	48
4.3 CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE FINDINGS	51
CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	53
5.1 CONCLUSION	53
5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS	55
REFERENCE	57
APPENDIX	62
APPENDIX 1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	62
APPENDIX 2: LINK OF THE ONLINE SURVEY	62
APPENDIX 3: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE	62
APPENDIX 4 PARTICIPATION INFORMATION FORM	65

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1: GENDER OF PARTICIPANTS	37
FIGURE 2: AGE GROUP OF PARTICIPANTS	38
FIGURE 3: BACKGROUND OF PARTICIPANTS	39
FIGURE 4: WORKING YEAR	40
FIGURE 5: PREFERENCE ABOUT TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION	41
FIGURE 6: AGREEABLENESS ABOUT TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION'S HELP TO PROVIDE EFFECTIVE HEALTH SERVICE	42
FIGURE 7: IMPACTS OF TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION	43
FIGURE 8: CHALLENGES FOR TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION	44
FIGURE 9: RATINGS OF NHS HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY	45
FIGURE 10: USE OF TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION	46
FIGURE 11: IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION ON HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY	47
FIGURE 12: IMPROVING QUALITY OF HEALTH SERVICE	48

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

One of the biggest achievement of the human civilisation is the immense development in the field of science and technology along with new inventions and innovations which have endowed human life with progress, prosperity, development, ease and convenience by revolutionising the way of living and enhancing the quality of life (Boyle *et al.*, 2011). Technological innovations are the changes and new advancements in products and process developed in the technological aspects (Khan and Khan, 2009). It has played a major role in the progress and development in every sector as it has touched every aspect of human life and every sector of business and development. There has been the influence of technological innovations in the health service sector. Health service refers to the services that are associated with the diagnosis and treatment of disease including promotion, prevention and restoration of the health which is provided by the health care professional who is specialised in those fields (Duncan and Breslin, 2009). It is one of the prominent services that could be needed by people in any stage of their life, and it is the basic right of people to have access to health care service throughout their life. The concept of health care service is not a new one, it dates back to the origin of human civilisation as physical and mental well-being is the requirement of healthy life, the only difference has been being in the ways of health service provision (Chang *et al.*, 2012).

WHO defines technological innovations in the health sector as the novel medical device solutions, which are invented to address health problems as well as enhance the quality of living. Technologies have allowed the health service sectors to make use of technological innovations to enhance their service quality with root to better provision of health service delivery. It has made a positive contribution to the development and advancement of health service sector and is one of the main contributors to take health service sector in today's highly sophisticated and advanced form. Akanksha Jayanthi (2014), in his article, has discussed some of the technological innovations in health care system within the last decade. It includes electronic health record, eHealth, telemedicine, telehealth, portal technology, remote monitoring tools, sensors and wearable technology, pharmacogenomics/genome sequencing and others. These are some of the latest technological innovations that have been used in the modern health care

system, which has brought advancement and development in recent health care. In the modern time, without technological innovations health sector could not deliver quality and effective health services. However, some the researches and studies consider adaptation of technological innovation to be challenging. Pesola (2013) states that the changes brought by technologies could take a long time to implement as it might be complex to change the attitude or behaviours of the health practitioners, the treatment system and the structure of the health care organization. Similarly, Hovlin, Arvidsson and Ljung (2013) viewed that as health care sector is associated with the life and health of the people, it is somehow more risky to experiment with new solutions in comparison to other sectors. On the other hand, some people argued that technology has made people machine dependent with no place for creativity. However, technological innovation is in itself an expanded form of creativity, and if one makes right use the technology is a blessing, it is how one perceives and makes its proper use (Windrum *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, almost all of the countries of the world use technological innovations in their health service sector including the UK. Romanelli, (2016), opines that for the next 20 years the UK has to spend in technology in health care system to grow and keep up with other countries. NHS is the public health service provider in UK, and it has make use of various technological innovations in their health service delivery (Windrum *et al.*, 2016). In this background, this study is an attempt to analyse the impact of technological innovations on health service delivery of NHS UK.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF THE RESEARCH ORGANIZATION

NHS is the abbreviated form of National Health Service. It is largest publically funded health care system in the UK established on 5th July 1948 with the core principle that good health care should be provided to all regardless of wealth. It provides free service to the residents of UK expectation to some charges in some of the cases like dental, optical and others. In the recent time, NHS provides service to more than 64.6 million people in the UK with 53.4 million people from England (Duncan and Breslin, 2009). Moreover, NHS has an innovation team that is focused on incorporating change and innovation for delivering excellent health service to the people (Chang *et al.*, 2012). This study highlights the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery basing in the case of NHS UK. Although it is a challenging task for NHS to make a right use of technologies to meet the need of its service user, NHS is always committed to provide best service to the people.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Health care service sector is one of the prominent sector that are required in each country. Although new and innovative technological inventions have been incorporated in the health sector, health service provider and the user have not been able to obtain intended benefits from those innovations. It is necessary for health service providers like NHS to analyze the technological innovation impact in term of delivering health services to the patients. This study tends to examine the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery at NHS UK. NHS UK has been incorporating technological innovations in their health service sector from the very early time to uplift the efficiency and productivity of the health sector. However, its outcomes are not always achieved quickly and cheaply. There has been high investment for technological innovations at NHS such as £260m integrated Digital Care fund in 2013 for digitalization of patients' information and medical propection system and Nursing Technology fund worth £65 m and many other investments. Moreover, NHS spends around £128bn every year for medical technology. However, NHS has not been able to deliver desired outcome from each of its investments, one of its instant is the NHS IT programme, which was launched with high aspiration but was abandoned in 2013. As NHS is government funded organization, the government of UK also wants to ensure that the investment is worth and delivering maximum benefits to the citizens. Thus, investigating the impact of technological innovations in the requirement of the current scenario. To analyze the impact, the researcher will be making use of quantitative data collection methods with the help of questionnaire survey to conduct the research. The survey will be conducted within London. It is anticipated that the survey would support the venture to examine the impact that technological innovations in health care delivery of UK.

1.4 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Health is one of the significant issues that are related to the well-being the people, the kind of service provided showcase the health status of the people and quality of their life (Kruk *et al.*, 2016).The concepts of technological innovations and health service have become a major concern and relevant issue in the recent time. This study intends to analyse the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery in the case of NHS UK. Thus making study

in such topic in itself an opportunity to make contribution in the health sector by making valuable findings which could be useful in practical basis (Chen *et al.*, 2014). The researcher believed that choosing the topic related to the well-being of the people and society can be a positive involvement from their side. Thus, the rationale for this study is to dig new insight on technological innovations and health service sector along with making a remarkable contribution in research field.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

NHS UK is making wide use of technological innovations in their health care system to enhance the quality of their service and to provide the best service to their service user. However, only a few attempts have been made to investigate the impacts of technological innovations on health service delivery. This study is focused on analysing the impact of technological innovation in health service delivery at NHS UK. As NHS is the major public health service provider in the UK, the issue associated with it are not connected with themselves only but also to the people and government. The study carries significance in term of its wide subject matter, which covers a wide area, and the findings derived from it will be beneficial from many angles. In general, the present study holds significance on the basis of its relevance to the health service sector as health sector is related to the well-being of the people, making study related to that sector will provide a noteworthy contribution to the well-being of the people. From a practical standpoint, this study will be a significant aid to overall health sector as it will research different aspects related to health sector, which could be applied practically in health sector.

1.6 RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The main aim of this research study is to examine the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery in the case of NHS UK. To achieve this aim, some of the objectives are set for this study which is as follows:

- To discover the technological innovations employed in NHS UK.
- To explore the features of the health service delivery in NHS.
- To analyse the impact of technological innovations on health service delivery of NHS UK.

- To find out the ways to improve the quality of service in health service sectors in UK and NHS UK.

1.7 RESEARCH QUESTION

The research questions with regards to this study are as follows.

1. What are the impacts of technological innovations on the health service delivery of NHS UK?
2. What are the health service and technological innovations that are into use in NHS UK?
3. What are the challenges that health sector has to face in the technological innovations system?
4. What are the ways to improve the service quality in health sectors in the UK?

1.8 STRUCTURE OF THE RESEARCH

This research is divided into five chapters which are described as below:

Chapter One: This is the opening chapter of this study. It commences with a brief background to the research and the research organisation followed by problem statement and rationale of the study. It is accompanied by the formation of research aims and objectives along with research questions. Likewise, the structure of the whole is presented in the last part of this chapter.

Chapter Two: This chapter opens with a theoretical framework for the study. Different literary sources related to health care service in the UK, technological innovations, challenges in health sectors, impacts of technological innovation and ways to improve health service quality are reviewed critically. Basing on these literature reviews, a conceptual framework is developed towards the end of this chapter.

Chapter Three: This chapter unfolds the research methodology used for this study with clear justification. It starts with research philosophy and approach along with research method, data collection and sampling methods. Likewise, validity and reliability, limitation and ethical consideration are disclosed.

Chapter four: In the part, the findings derived from the study are presented in graphical form, and they are analysed properly for its validity and reliability. Likewise, the findings are discussed to drive the outcomes.

Chapter Five: This is the last chapter of this study. Basing on the findings of the research conclusion are drawn, and it ensures if the set aims and objectives are fulfilled or not. In the last part, appropriate recommendations are provided.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

There is hardly any sector where technological innovations are not incorporated, and in the case of health service sector, it is one of the most vital aspects. In the health sector, technological innovations are incorporated in information and communication technology, in a medical instrument, medicine, in the ways of diagnosis and treatment, in research and development and other aspects (Romanelli, 2016). It has truly generated noteworthy contribution in the health sector to enhance the quality and standard. Various studies have been conducted regarding the use of technological innovations in the health sector and about the impacts that it has made in the overall health sector. Mauro Romanelli in his research study depicts that, technology has set the background for development in health care sector with innovation and patient-centred care by making improvement in quality as well as the efficiency of health care services. Health care organisations make use of technological innovations in align with policies for enhancement in effective health care services (Georgiadis and Mehl, 2016). The technological innovations are one of the key reason to the development and advancement of the health sector along with quality and standard service delivery. Likewise, in the report of Elie Geisler (2008) about the role of technology in healthcare delivery, it is illustrated that technology enables people expectations and medical and administrative capacity of enhanced diagnosis, global reach and miracle cures, it is the contributory tool in the modern health care and medicine.

In the research conducted by Paula Ranta (2010), about information and communication technology in health care the role of ICT in increasing the health care productivity, issues associated with it and cause of slow adaptation of ICT has been deliberate with the aid of the collection of wide range of secondary data and information. By the study, it was found that in spite of its limitation, ICT makes an impact on the productivity of the health sector, makes changes in the health care procedures and ICT supports in the shift from acute care to prevention and self-care approach that is beneficial in term of both health and economy. In the study of Sachdeva (2001), it is depicted that, use of new technology might demand high cost, but if care is given in the selection process, the use of apt technology leads to cost –effective care that has long term benefits. In spite of being a costly approach, with right selection and use of

technologies in the health sector, sustainable advantage can be gained through technological innovations. Some of these research papers and report can be taken as a basis to have insight on the impact of technological innovations on the health service delivery. More detail analysis has been provided in subsequent headings.

2.2 HEALTH CARE SERVICES IN UK

Health care service is the prominent service that is necessary to all people in every stage of their life (Romanelli, 2016). It is the fundamental right of the people to get access to health care services in respect of their race, religion, social or economic condition and others. The provision of health care is the basis for quality of living, without health care service the quality of life can't be enhanced. WHO (1948) defines health as the state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, not only the absence of disease or infirmity. A healthy person is not characterised by merely the absence of disease; they have to be physically, psychologically and socially well, then only they are considered healthy (Weber *et al.*, 2014). Every individual has the right to have access to health services, and every nation of the world is responsible for providing quality health service to their citizen.

In term of UK, UK is a well-developed nation in Europe, with development and advancement in every sector including the health sector. WHO (2000) has ranked the health service of UK at 18th position out of 191 nations. This shows the provision of good and standard health service of the UK being in the initial position. NHS is the main public health service provider in the UK. It constitutes the public healthcare sector in the UK and was established in 1948 with the long-held ideal that quality health care should be provided to all men, women and children irrespective of their wealth. This has given birth to free health service facilities to the UK citizen exception to some case such as dental service, optical and others. E.Hawe, P.Yuen and L. Ballie (2011) presents that in UK public sector, health expenses constitute 87% of the total health expenditure in the financial year 2007/2008. This is the evidence for the fact that UK health sector is embodied with the majority of the public sector in comparison to the private sector health sector (Adams *et al.*, 2016). NHS is the public health service provider organization in UK. The health service structure of NHS UK is divided into primary and secondary health care service.

According to Mant et al. (2000), this kind of health service structure is pervasive with the advent of specialist concept in the health care service.

Although NHS and the government of UK have played a vital role in uplifting the health status of the citizen at the same time, there are some of the other sides of government involvement. Some of its negative impacts are dwindled in the function of market mechanism and controlled health expenditure that led to the inadequate supply of medical instruments, resources and medical personals (Duncan and Breslin, 2009).

2.3 TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN HEALTH SECTOR AND NHS UK

The rapid development of science and technology has paved ways for the technological innovations that have proved to be a blessing for the entire human being (Khan and Khan, 2009). Technological innovation has supplement advancement, development, progress and prosperity in every sector; it has added ease, comfort, convenience and success in the life of people making it worth living. Holland (2011) defined innovation as the successful utilisation of new ideas and the activity of bringing new idea or product in the market. In health, sector innovations are mostly associated with the technologies. Technological innovations are the new or innovative technology, products or process or the significant changes (Romanelli, 2016). It has changed not only change the face of the industrial sector but also the health care sector and has taken it into a today's' desirable height. On the other hand, Gupta (2008) put forward the view that although hospitals and other health service provider proved to be fast to adopt the technological innovations in the medical instruments and treatment procedures, less focus is given to networking and communication innovations which could be due to attention for security and patient privacy and also the health care is provided locally and in person.

Tom Page (2014) in his study has discussed the role of innovations in the healthcare sector of UK. The author stated that innovations are one of an essential aspects of health care and in the case of NHS it is the major means that has driven NHS to the present condition. The technological innovations have brought distinctive benefits to the health professional and service user of NHS. Some of the examples of technological innovation of NHS UK are KwickScreen (Korn, 2011), a screen design for patient safety and HCAI Technology Innovative Programme. This paper has present the limelight on the use of technological innovation in NHS UK and how

it has directed NHS in a prominent position. According to May et al. (2002), one of the instance of technological innovation in NHS is the adaptation of “telehealth care system” which has to enable the synchronization the communication of patients with their service provider. In 1998 to be in align with technological changes and integrating it with the system, NHS bring forward the Information for Health: an Information Strategy for NHS 1998-2005 that laid foundations to various technological innovations that were followed by NHS establishment of National Programme for IT in 2002 which is now called Connecting for health. Some of its achievements are as follows:

- Electronic patient records: establish for putting detail record of the information about the diagnosis, treatment and care information of the patients.
- Electronic health records: recording wide range data and information related to health care.
- Technical infrastructure: NHS networking, a dictionary of clinical terms as well as strategic messaging service.
- Health care information system: Enhancing the access of service user and clinician to health service information.
- Telemedicine and telecare: Guidelines on how to use them.

Likewise, in 2014 NHS England has formed National Information Board to be in align with the Technology –enabled care (TEC) strategy of the government. In the review of Lord Drazzi about NHS, there has been a highlight in the significance of technology in health service and in term of legal duty that is put to the health officials to endorse innovations.

2.4 CHALLENGES FOR TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN HEALTH SERVICE SECTOR

Although technological innovations have been the backbone of the development and innovations in the health service sector, there are various challenges that come in the way of technological innovations in the health service sector. The CGI on the report about “Healthcare challenges and trends” has depicted the challenges and trends that are in the health sector. In their white paper, they have mentioned that rising costs, demographic changes, easy access, quality focus and customer driven service are some of the key issues that healthcare sector has to face and the

global health trends are patient focused medical home, informed service user and rise in use of social media, patient's choice, personalized medicine, hospital network and others. Globalisation has established a global trend in health care system which has additional challenges to health care sector (Ranta, 2010). Likewise, in term of technological innovations, Robert et al. (2009) point out four challenges that health care sector organisation faces in the adaptation of technology:

- Improving organisational decision making process in term of technological innovations adaptation (involving senior management, clinician and stakeholder for considering technological innovations).
- Enhancing the adaptive capacity of the organisation to new knowledge related to technological innovations (recruitment, training and development to the staffs about innovations).
- Developing receptive organisational context for technological innovation (communicating with stakeholders).
- Cultivating organisational readiness for a particular innovation (preparing organisation to adapt to technological innovations)

Likewise, according to Christensen and Remler (2007), some of the challenges in the adaptation of ICT in the health sector are little product differentiation, switching cost and technical compatibility death. In the health sector, each service user has own kind of need; different service is needed to them. The health information is wide in nature, for an instant a disease can be different in a different situation. The ICT that is appropriate for one group might be inappropriate for another group; low product differentiation has been a barrier for ICT adaptation (Windrum *et al.*, 2016).

On the other hand, some of the scholars consider the shortage of health professional as one of the major challenges in the health service innovation (Omachonu and Einspruch, 2010). Warne and MCandrew, (2002) states that the lack of nurses and skilled professional is another aspect of healthcare innovation, this condition has been aggravated by the rise in the superannuation of the recent staffs in upcoming ten years. But Hill, Langvard and Massey (2007), viewed that the challenges that come in the way of eHealth innovation are the operational, legal and economic

constraints. In innovative product development, there should be a global standard, data security, patient friendly approach and easy access to data and information should be maintained (Jamal *et al.*, 2009). Another challenge in technological innovation is the financial aspect, it is a costly approach, which adds economic burden to the healthcare organisation.

2.5 IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS ON HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY

There has been a rise in the use of various technologies in health care sector as technological innovation has added many new inventions to the sector. And has revolutionised the entire health care system. High competition in the health sector, an abrupt rise in need of health care service, the emergence of new and complex diseases, new medical areas of technological application and regulatory obligations has led to the rising pressure in the application of technological innovation in the health care system. In the recent, almost every area of health care sector is covered up by technological innovations, and they are making maximum utilisation of it. The growing utilisation of technological innovations in health care sector has the urge to analyse its impact on the health care delivery (Ranta, 2010). Various scholars, researchers, researchers and studies have underpinned different impact that technological innovation has made on the health service delivery. According to Friedman (2000), the new technological acquisition could be taken as one of the critical decision of the hospital management which could have a vivid impact on the hospital. This shows the impact of making use of technological innovations in the health service sector; the technology acquisition has made a remarkable impact on the health sectors or the hospitals Manish Kurhekar, and Joydip Ghosal (2010) in their study have found that information technology has played major role in entire health care sector like providing quality health care to the service user in reasonable price, keeping patient history record, case management, providing referral, EMRs for accurate and fast information processing and others. However, Adam (2003) hold a different view regarding the technological impact on the health sector; he argued that rapid speed of technological development and research discovery has exceeded the capability of health service to acclimate the changes and has led to disentanglement of medical innovation with organisational growth (Angst, 2007).

The technological innovation in health care system has played a remarkable role to improve the health care delivery. According to Bush (2004), the innovation in term of electronic records and

medical information exchange would help to transmute the health care with the uplifting quality of health care, avoiding medical errors, decreasing cost in health care, upgrading administrative efficiencies, decreasing paperwork and upsurge to reasonable health service access. This quote from the Bush Administration's Health IT plan implies the impact of Information technologies in the health care sector of the United States which connotes the positive impact that health information technology brings in the entire health care sector of the country (Adams *et al.*, 2016). In a similar way, Schoen et al. (2005) opine that health information provides various benefits in administrative works like reduction in paper works, improve in administrative efficiencies along with a reduction in workload to health practitioners and increasing access to affordable care Chertow et al. (2001) in their research have found that the implementation of health information technology (HIT) has support in providing appropriate doses to the patients which have exhibited its efficiency in reduction of medical errors through imposing clinical guidelines and care procedures. The health information innovations have increased the administrative system, increasing people access to health care and decrease in medical error which in broad term has implied affirmative impact. Shortliffe, (2005) hold the differential view, he asserts that HIT is majority headed at the health system, payer and service user with fewer advantages appreciated by the GP. This shows in comparison to health professionals; patients are more benefitted by HIT. However, it has been found that HIT brings equal benefits to the service provider as well, Ambinder (2005) states that Electronic health recorder (HIT) is an effective means to link care setting and develop collaboration, it is the corresponding approach for the caregiver and improves the monitoring and tracing of the patients care activities. Bessant et al. (2012) assert that the by the exclusion of radical innovations in health care, it is not possible to sustain the desired health care services in the highly developed societies. The health care sector has perceived its present form of development and advancement only just because of technological innovations. Furthermore, Gupta (2008) points out the four main ways by which health care system is impacted by the technological innovations with revolutionising system that includes an increase in offshore services, monitoring of drug safety at global level, incorporation of health information system and improved health quality information system to health professionals and patients.

On the other side Maisonneuve (2005) argued that in the last decade, the health care spending has risen quicker than the aggregate income, the technological innovations and the relative price

tend to impact on the health care expenditure development. In the case of UK, the government of UK have to increase their investment in NHS health investment as without adequate budget technological innovations could not be adopted to health care system. NHS spend around £128bn every year for medical technology. However, with healthcare spending and budgets, people could be provided with quality and standard health service by which the spending is not taken in a negative way. The health care sector has been delivering enhanced service to the service user with the introduction of new medicines and costly medical treatment equipment by which there has been an increase in health expenditures. The development in medical technology has provided a favourable platform to provide improved service to the individual service users (Boyle *et al.*, 2011). The cost is acknowledged as by the help of technological innovations in health service sector they are getting easy diagnosis and treatment for various health complications (Ranta, 2010). Nevertheless, health care sector is highly impacted by the technological innovations, in spite of its some negative impact; technological innovations have impacted the health care sector in a positive way with upliftment and development of sector and improvement in healthcare delivery.

2.6 WAYS TO IMPROVE HEALTH SERVICE QUALITY IN UK

The provision of quality health care service is the fundamental right of the citizen. It is the duty of the government to provide quality health care to its citizen and work towards enhancing the quality of living of the people (Ranta, 2010). Good physical, mental and psychological well-being contributes in uplifting the quality of life of the people. The technological inventions have transformed the entire medical and health service towards better perspective with diagnosis and treatment of various kind of disease with a decrease in mortality rate (Hussain, 2015). In UK, NHS is providing quality, safe and standard health care service to the people. It is committed to provide best possible service to its citizens with the provision of various kinds of health services. Though there has been huge development and advancement in health service sector that has inclined health sector in its prominent position; the sector is always in the urge of improvement. Donabedian (2003) states that improvement in quality of healthcare can be done with the use of various methods centralized to upgrade healthcare by developing more effective and efficient care system and enhancing the safety of service user or patient. Health care system should always directed towards improving the quality, then only service user could gain maximum

benefits from the health care system. One of the major way to improve the quality of health care service is the development of effective communication channel both within internal and external level. This means building good level of communication among health professionals, stakeholders and between service provider and service user. According to Pirnejad H et al. (2007) to endow effectual and quality care, effective communication is mandatory mainly to the healthcare institute and service providers who are working on same group of patients or disease. For the delivery of quality, health care there should be good communication between clinician and patients, service provider and users. The modern information technology allows the flow of information and data in a safe, easy and reliable way. However, health care providers are failing to build effective communication medium, Donaldson (2002) asserts that lack of communication to exchange detail, relevant and precise information with in healthcare interfaces is a prime avoidable issue to patient safety. On the other hand, Ewan B. Ferlie and Stephen M. Shortell (2001) in their study has depicted core properties for enhancing the quality of health which consists of leadership approach, organizational culture, team development and information technology. Visionary leaders at the health care organization, organizational culture with strong team bond that focuses on quality health service delivery could contributes in the quality upliftment. Likewise, the right and time relevant use of various medical and information technologies helps to upgrade the standard and quality of health service provided.

2.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This research tends to analyse the impact of technological innovations in the health service delivery. Through the literature review, the insights about technological innovations and healthcare sector in the UK has been explored. Likewise, the impact of technological innovations, challenges for technological impacts and ways to improve the health care services is analysed with the help of information collected through various literary sources (Romanelli, 2016). In the research study, conceptual framework comprehends the researcher towards the accomplishment of research aims and objectives and provides a framework for the whole research study. It provides limelight on the relationship among different variables basing on the findings made by the literature review. For this study, the figure of conceptual framework in Appendix 1 shows the relationship between different variable, technological innovations, health sector and health service delivery. Technological innovations and health service sector are

independent variables as they don't depend other factors while health service delivery is the dependent variable. The health service delivery is dependent variable as it is depended on different aspects of the health sector and technological innovations and the impact that technological innovations have over it. The health service primarily does diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases and conduct various researches related to disease and health sector. Likewise, medical technologies, IT and technical infrastructure are some of the technological innovations employed in the health sector. Form the literature review it is found that technological innovations have both positive and negative impact on the health service delivery; the positive impacts are the increased efficiency, improved service and reduction in medical errors whereas the negative impact is the cost factor and technical errors. The conceptual for this study on the ground of literature review is illustrated in appendix 1.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 OVERVIEW

The current section details the methodological approaches that the researcher used to accomplish the research objectives specified in the preceding chapter. The current section outlines the various systematic approaches that were used to find the answer to the research questions and goes further to explain why the methods were deemed to be appropriate and valid. It is also within the intention of the researcher to focus on the techniques that were deployed in data collection, which will pave the way for a detailed discussion of the methods that were implemented in data analysis, including the quantitative approaches that were used. The paper reveals that the whole research took a month. The preparation of the project in the identification of the subject matter and the literature search took one week, the data collection process was conducted in one-week duration, data analysis took another week, and the report writing was also conducted in a week. The section takes a typical approach to identify, evaluate, and analyse the procedure utilised in that collection as well as results or findings. Particular attention has been directed towards explaining the data analysis procedures used in this study. As such, the paper presents a detailed discussion of methods, the difference between approaches, and research design.

3.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Research philosophy is the specific assumption or belief of the researcher in regards to the preparation of the research study (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). It is necessary to define certain phenomena on which basis data and information are collected, analysed to reach a valid conclusion. Primarily, the research philosophy is apprehensive with the individual's insights and perception about particular issues that ultimately impact the method and design selected for the research study (White and McBurney, 2012). There are three types of research philosophies

namely, realism, positivism, and interpretivism. Realism philosophy is associated with the scientific facts in concern with developing information (Graziano and Raulin, 2012). It assumes that the presence of objects and happenings are independent to the human mind instead they occur in isolation. This assumption is grounded on that side of reality that is allied ontologically with the conceptual values and ideas. On the other hand, positivism philosophy grasps valid knowledge on the subject matter through an investigation where the research is more valid and accurate. In this philosophy, predictions are made by previous findings, and the opinion of the researcher relies on the facts. It could also be compared with the scientific experiment. It observes studies and various variables under a controlled situations on which basis outcomes are derived (Matthews and Ross, 2010). Whereas interpretivism philosophy is usually subjective, this philosophy assumes human behaviours rely on the way they interpret the situation they faced. Interpretivism philosophy applies to have an understanding of the particular situation that happens at the time of research study (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). As this study intends to analyse the impact of technological innovations in health service delivery in NHS UK, positivism research philosophy has been implied.

Justification of using positivism

The positivism research philosophy is appropriate for this study because the outcomes of the research are based on various types of experiments instead of just going with the results which already exists. With the use of the experimental method, this study has been able to gather fresh knowledge, which has only been possible with the use of positivist philosophy. The positivist philosophy allows the researcher to collect factual data with the use of different methods (survey questionnaire), thus to make factual findings and reach into valid and accurate conclusion, positivism philosophy has been used. One of the advantages of positive philosophy is that it is consistent with the quantitative data. Thus, in this research positivism philosophy can effectively achieve the research objectives and provides the better result of the research.

3.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

Research approach denotes the method that has been applied to conduct the research study (White and McBurney, 2012). Commonly, there are two kinds of research approach, one is inductive research approach, and the other is deductive research approach. Primarily they

differentiate in term of the significance of hypothesis in the research study (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). In an inductive approach, there is movement from specific to general. In this approach, research commences with observation and ends with the formulation of new theories along with its generalisation, there is no hypothesis testing, and the conclusion is derived by observation (Dawson, 2013). On the other hand, in deductive approach, there is movement from general to specific. It is centred to causality starting with a hypothesis or research question. This approach tends to test the theories and hypothesis with narrowing down to make it more specific towards the end. In this study, the deductive approach has been applied as it apt to inspect the existing theories to evaluate the impact of technological innovations in the health sector.

Justification for the use of Deductive approach

One of the reasons for selecting a deductive approach for this study is that this study doesn't aim to construct any new theories rather it aims to analyse the impact of technological innovations in the health service delivery at NHS UK. The benefits of using deductive approach are that it is suitable for creating a connection between foundation and conclusion. Research questions or hypothesis were created at the initial part of the study for reaching into appropriate conclusion towards the end. In the study, prevailing theories were tested for validity and for drawing a valid conclusion, previous research finding was considered, and data were collected. With the use of deductive approach, the researcher was able to analyse the technological innovations impact over health care delivery.

3.4 RESEARCH TECHNIQUE

The researcher has deployed a longitudinal survey technique. Scholars argue that survey methodologies are compatible with two fundamental types of techniques including cross-sectional survey technique and the longitudinal survey technique. The cross-sectional research technique is more practical in the investigation of variables that are not time sensitive, and when the study involves a large population. On the contrary, the longitudinal technique must be used within a specific and significant population over a specified period. Longitudinal and cross sectional techniques can also be differentiated by the fact that, the first involves the gathering of some or readily available data in specific intervals. This study utilised a longitudinal survey as

the researcher used the survey questionnaires to collect data about issues based on the perception, and opinions of the defined population.

3.5 RESEARCH METHOD/DESIGN

To have a wider examination of the subject matter, it is necessary to make a selection of suitable research method according to the subject matter. There is a various method of conducting research; the commonly used methods are the qualitative and quantitative research methods. The qualitative research method is used to have the insight of underlying reasons, view and problems on specific subject matter and in exploratory in nature (Creswell, 2014). It makes use of unstructured or semi structured pattern where the focus is given on revealing the behaviour and perception of people on the certain matter. In quantitative research, the population sample size is large, and data are collected with the use of survey methods. In this research study, the researcher has applied Quantitative research method along with survey questionnaire.

Justification for the use of Quantitative research method

One of the reasons for choosing the quantitative research method is that it quantifies the statistical data and permits to generalise the results derived from the sample selected from the total population. This method has been one the appropriate method to collect relevant data and information related to the subject matter.

Research Design

This study utilised the quantitative research design that focused on the collection of quantitative data using questionnaires. The primary data in this study was gathered through the use of structured questionnaires that were sent to participants over the Internet. The construction of these research instruments was done by the researcher after a thorough review of the literature concerning the impact of technological innovations on healthcare service delivery. The notion that the researcher chose a quantitative approach to study justified the idea that the questionnaire included structured items or questions that restricted the participants to attain only relevant answers to research questions. What is more, a five-point Likert scale was applied in structuring questions that gauged the participants' perceptions. The quantitative approach of the study investigates the actual impact of technological innovations on health outcomes as a measure of

the quality of the service delivered in the facility. The questionnaire survey was based on the review of literature pieces that acted as rich sourced of secondary data as well as concepts that were used to develop the foundation of the study. The questionnaire was carefully structured in such a way that guarantees the chances of the participants to understand the kind of responses that the researcher needed them to provide.

Among the strategies used to simplify the questionnaire was the logical arrangement of questions, the elimination of ambiguity in questioning, the use of non-technical terms, and the use of appropriate definition in situations that demanded the use of technical words (Bryman, 2015a). Ambiguous and imprecise concepts or words were avoided for the reduction of errors in responses to the questions of the questionnaire survey (Kumar, 2014). Double- negative or double- barreled questions were also avoided to reduce the chances of any confusion in the questions (Thomas, 2013). Surveys must not use items that could create biases or those that lead respondents towards providing a particular answer because of such support pre- formulated that downplay the accuracy and objectivity of findings. As such, questionnaires leading questions and those that are suggestive were eliminated to support the production of reliable and valid results (Walliman, 2015).

The questionnaire was selected because it provides first-hand data that is easily quantifiable. The responses obtained can be easily converted into numeric forms suitable for quantitative analysis of data.

The quality and reliability of data will be assessed through comparative analysis. In which case, the data and results obtained will be compared to those derived from the existing literature to evaluate its consistency with literature. Outliers will be identified and placed under consideration during data analysis

3.6 RESEARCH STRATEGY

Likewise, suitable research strategy is to be made for carrying out the research study. The research study is the plan or framework on which basis the study will be conducted so that the set

aims and objectives will be fulfilled and the research question will seek answers. It is helpful in researching a well-organised way by choosing apt data collection method along with its analysis to reach an appropriate conclusion. Basing on the subject matter of the research study various strategies are made into use (Bryman, 2015b). In term of scientific research, most experiments are done whereas in normal research other strategies are used. Some of these research strategies are described as below:

3.6.1 EXPERIMENTS

The experiment is associated with the positive philosophical position (Graziano and Raulin, 2012). Thus it aims to approve or disapprove research hypothesis. It is primarily based on observations and tests for making findings. It provides limelight into the cause and effect nature with the outcome by manipulating single variable. Experiments are more appropriate for scientific research as this research is to be conducted for health service sector being specific to NHS UK, thus here experiment is not suitable.

3.6.2 CASE STUDY

Case studies imply researching certain case scenario. In the case of study approach, a specific case is chosen to insight about a particular topic. It is usually done when a researcher needs to study about a specific group, people or company within given environment (Creswell and Clark, 2011). This study aims to analyse the impact of technological innovation in the health sector. Thus NHS UK was chosen as case study to examine the technological innovation impact on health outcomes in the UK, public health sector.

3.6.3 SURVEY

The survey is conducted to obtain accurate data about the specific subject matter from a target group. It tends to evaluate the correlations among variables to measure the gathered data. For doing a survey, a sample size is selected as the representative of the total population, and generally, the questionnaire is prepared for conducting the surveys (White and McBurney, 2012). In the present research survey methods has been employed to analyse the impact of technological

innovations on health service delivery of NHS UK by collecting data and information from the target group.

Justification for the use of survey and case study

In the present research study, the researcher has made use of survey and case study as the research strategy as by both of these methods relevant data and information regarding the impact of technological innovations in NHS UK can be collected and analysed (Kumar, 2014). The case study method has helped to make study basing on NHS UK as NHS covers the public health sector, the case has made it possible to have a wider study of the public health sector in the UK. Likewise, the survey is considered as one of the most suitable method for collection of primary sources of data by selection of appropriate respondents. Moreover, survey is cost effective, fast and easy method. As this research is time and financial resource constraint, survey method seemed more suitable for the researcher. An online survey was conducted for this study. With the use of survey and case study the study was able to fulfill the set aims and objectives of this study.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

In all types of the research study, data and information hold significant position without which the research could not be completed. Data are essential aspects to make findings on any of the specific subject matter (Bryman, 2015b). There is two kinds of data; they are the primary source of data and secondary source of data. In this research study both the secondary source of data and primary source of data has been collected by making use of different data collection tools and methods.

3.7.1 SECONDARY SOURCE OF DATA

Secondary sources of data are those kinds of data that are previously collected and published by others. It is pre-existing data. Thus it requires less time, effort and energy of the researcher in compare to the primary source of data (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). These types of data are collected through research paper, journals, article, reports, books, online source, government and private statics and others. In the present research, the secondary data have been collected from scholars view, previous research paper, journals and different online sources relevant to the subject matter.

3.7.2 PRIMARY SOURCE OF DATA

Primary sources of data are those data that is collected by the researcher themselves on their effort (Creswell, 2014). Primary data are first hand, and fresh data that is collected by conducting research thus are taken as data that are more precise. However, it consumes more time, energy and effort in comparison to secondary data. For a collection of primary data, techniques like survey, questionnaire, interview etc. are used.

The title ‘Analyzing the Impact of Technological Innovation on Health Service Delivery: A Case Study of NHS UK’ shows that this study is quantifiable since there are clear dependent and independent variables. In this case, the dependent variable is health service delivery while the independent variable is technological innovations, which are parameters whose relationship can be established through a suitable quantitative data collection method like a questionnaire.

In the case of this research, the researcher has applied online survey questionnaire method. A fully structured questionnaire was prepared in align with the research aims and objectives. The questionnaire contains set of questions related to the subject matter that is filled up by the participants (Creswell, 2014). It is one of the most suitable instruments for surveying as it helps to collect first-hand data from many participants at a time. In this research, the questionnaire of the online survey was filled up by the 60 respondents that include both the staffs and patients of NHS UK. This primary data collection technique is flexible enough to allow adequate control over the information of the data that is collected. Furthermore, the notion that the information that is gathered through primary research is created by the researcher or the author of the study implies that it responds to the exact need of the study, which augments the contextualization of results. The major advantage or benefit of employing online questionnaire survey technique is the improvement in the response rate. This is because it is significantly easy to access the information on the researcher’s part and the respondents had an easy time answering the questionnaire on the respondent’s part. As implied in the research design section of my study,

primary research has numerous advantages as it bridges the gap between theories and practice in research by allowing the researcher and the population to share information and opinions.

The consent request was sent to the participants through their email. The respondents were requested to take part in the survey based on voluntary participation criterion. In this case, the participants were requested to click a link that would direct them to the survey questions if they were willing to take part in the study. By clicking the link, the participants were directly presented with the survey questions in the form of questionnaires. After that, the database collected their answers and provided them to the researcher for analysis. Hence, the data was collected using the online platform. High level of validity and reliability of the findings was anticipated upon confirming that the questionnaire was well-structured and that all items were developed in a manner that encourages participants to produce relevant but unique answers

The use of the survey questionnaire as a data collection method was convenient to the study because of the lack of a direct contact between the researcher and the respondents. Questionnaires are an easy way of conducting such research because the questionnaires could be sent to the respondent via email and later collected after submission by the respondents. Questionnaires are a great form of collecting primary data, as the researcher can collect feedback directly from the clients. However, caution must be exercised when using questionnaire since they require a high level of literacy as special care should be taken to ensure that the accurate understanding of responses is achieved. Also, the selection of the respondent sample should be carefully made to ensure that all respondents have a certain level of literacy since they will have to fill out the questionnaire forms by themselves. The design of questionnaires focuses on simplicity and clarity to maximize return rates. The questionnaire allows for the provision of various types of responses as required by the research. The questionnaires contain multiple-choice questions, structured questions with blank areas to be filled and open-ended questions where the respondent is encouraged to respond at length. The multiple-choice questions are preferred for quantitative data collection since they give out structured data according to the variables of this study.

3.8 POPULATION SAMPLING

Any survey could not be carried out without the presence of the participant as they provide relevant data and information about the subject matter. Population sampling is the process of taking some representative sample from the whole population (Thomas, 2013). Probability and non-probability sampling are the two types of sampling methods. In the probability sampling method, each member has a fixed probability of selection to be a part of the sample. Probability sampling gives every member an equal chance of selection. On the other hand, in non-probability sampling, there is no specific chance for each unit of population to be selected as the sample participant. This type of sampling is applied according to the convenient, preference and circumstance of the research study. Although, probability sampling is considered to be best sampling method where there are no biases from the side of the researcher in all case, it couldn't be use due to research context, time constraints, and differential nature of the population along with difficulty to access them.

This study has utilised a purposive non-probability sampling technique to select respondents (Bryman, 2015a). By this method, the researcher has selected sample participants being selected according to the objectives of the study and population characteristics. This study seeks to collect its data from the population of NHS UK patients and employees. The sample was chosen from the population of patients and employees of the NHS UK. The sample constitutes of participants who accepted to take part in the study and submit their responses to the online survey in total anonymity.

This study was conducted based on a sample of 60 respondents (NHS staffs and patients) selected using purposive sampling technique.

3.9 RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The questionnaire is one of the instruments of the study. The questionnaires were sent and received over the online (Qwik surveys) database, which was considered a more convenient and less expensive means of their distribution and gathering (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Likert scale is a type of measurement tool or data collection method that researchers employ in structuring the items (questions) embodying the questionnaires that were sent to participants over the internet. The researcher used the Likert scale to measure the opinions and perception of participants regarding the impact of; technological innovations in health service delivery. A

typical Likert scale consists of a set of items that occur in the form of judgments or claims that indicate the level of the reaction of participants to a particular question. The reaction typically ranges from extremely positive to absolutely negative or favourable to absolutely unfavourable, allowing respondents to choose one position of the five choices (level of reactions provided) (Cohen *et al.*, 2011). A five-point Likert scale was deployed in the development of the questionnaires that were used to gather information in this study.

3.10 DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis is one of the vital parts in the research study as the collected data and information must be analysed to draw a valid conclusion (Easton, 2010). Data analysis are of two types, qualitative and quantitative data analysis. The qualitative data analysis method permits in-detail and complete understanding of the fundamental reasons and motivations; it allows a fine distinction to be drawn as there is no need to place data into a finite number of classification (Cohen *et al.*, 2011). However, the findings from qualitative analysis couldn't be extended to a large population at the same level as in the case of quantitative analysis. In quantitative analysis, features are classified and statistical models are used to explain what is observed or found (Dawson, 2013). It allows the researcher to generalise the results to the entire population and measure the frequency of various views and estimations. In the present study, the collected data were in quantitative. Thus qualitative data analysis method was applied. The study was based on survey questionnaire, the questionnaire responses of the participants were analysed to fulfil the aims and objectives of the study. The numeric approach permitted the researcher to generate a relationship of responses of the respondents and behavioural aspects. The collected data and information were analysed with the help of SPSS tools. Likewise, the data has been presented and analysed in graphical form with the use of tables and figures. With quantitative data analysis, the impact of technological innovations in the health service delivery of NHS UK was explored with generating valid conclusion in aid of data analysis.

The data analysis process has been carried out in four stages. The initial step of data analysis is data reduction that focuses on summarisation of data. The data reduction step reduces the bulk of data obtained via the literature into brief and concise information (Easton, 2010). As such, under this stage, the researcher retrieves only the relevant and applicable information in a manner that

captures all concepts from the findings and eliminates repetition. The data reduction phase yields information that is directly consistent with the study's objective. The second step is data presentation. Under the second stage, the researcher uses the reduced data to develop diagrammatic representations that make it easy to understand the different aspect of the information obtained at first glance (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). Data representation used in this study utilizes descriptive statistics and other measures of central tendencies. Such observations result in the precise display of research findings and enhance understandability of information. The third stage is the description of the diagrammatic representations. Such reports ensure that every information is described in a way that eliminates confusion. The report describes the statistics, proportions, and all other concepts represented in the diagrams. The last stage entails drawing conclusions and making inferences (White and McBurney, 2012). The concluded are formulated in a manner that responds directly to the thesis statement by either supporting or opposing it. The inference is further supported by direct answers to the research questions that show evidence of significance, depending on whether the thesis statement is supported on rejected (Bhaskar, 2008).

3.11 RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

For deriving appropriate findings in a research study, data and information collected from various source should be reliable and valid. One of the major issues that should be considered in the research study is the reliability and validity of the data collected as the findings of the study are based on collected data and information (Bhaskar, 2008). In the present study, the researcher has made use of different measures for ensuring reliability and validity of data. As this study has employed both primary and secondary source of data and information, reliability and validity of both types of data were ensured. In the collection of secondary data, only authentic and genuine source was consulted, and the primary sources of data were collected from valid respondents. Collecting data from authentic and valid source helped in ensuring the reliability and validity of the data (Thomas, 2013). Similarly, analysis of data with the use of various analytical tool aids in confirming the validity of collected data. In the present research study, the use of various previous works on the similar subject matter has supported to ensure the reliability of findings. Reliability and validity of research ensure that the finding of this research is accurate and match to the findings of a previous research study in the similar subject matter. Likewise, various

statistical tools like SPSS were used to ensure the validity of the findings. In overall, the researcher has attempted to ensure the validity and reliability of the whole research.

3.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical consideration is another major thing that should be taken with significance while conducting the research (Saunders et al., 2015). It enables the researcher to research a dignified way without desecration of ethical rules. Research ethics are the principles, morals, guidelines or code of conducts which should be followed throughout the research study (Easton, 2010). It helps to uphold the quality of the research study and ensure the protection of intellectual property in the same way. Likewise, it said to ensure the right and welfare of the participants of the research and fulfilment of researcher responsibility towards the society. While conducting the research, research ethics should be firmly taken into consideration, and it should be ensured that all the ethical rules are followed thoroughly, and no any type of harm is done to anyone through conducting the research study.

While conducting this research, the researcher has paid attention to make consideration of research ethics and has endeavoured to follow them in the best possible way (Walliman, 2015). This present research is not targeted to any individual, group, society, race or religion and it is ensured that no harm is done to anyone through conducting the research. This research has been done with full dedication, sincerity, honesty; confidentiality and truthfulness with thorough follow of research ethics. The data and information collected through the secondary sources were included in the study only after mentioning credit to the original authors. Similarly, while conducting the survey, no any individual was forced to take part in it, the participants willing to take part in the survey were only chosen as the participants and process were forwarded only after their full consent. Likewise, to prevent the disclosure of their identity, the policy of confidentiality and privacy was used. The data and information collected were stored safely and it was away from access to any unauthorised person (White and McBurney, 2012). The permission to conduct the study was not presented as the survey was based on the online database(Qwik surveys) Moreover, no any data and information were misused and misinterpreted in any other form. The researcher has tried to maintain ethical consideration throughout the study by strictly following research ethics.

3.13 RESEARCH LIMITATION AND ACCESSIBILITY ISSUES

This research was conducted with the use of different methodological approaches, which have been described above, and to minimise any error; various precautions were taken. However, there were some limitations as well. This research was carried out to analyse the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery of NHS UK, for that data and information from the service provider and service user was required. For that purpose, survey method was used. However, the attitude of the participants was one of the major restraints in this process. Few of the participants, at first show their willingness to participate in the research but in a later phase, they drift away from research by which the researcher felt difficult to manage another participant at the last hour. Likewise, the limitation was in the part of findings of the research, as some of the respondents might not have provided full and true information. Another limitation of this research study was lack of sufficient resources and limited period. The research was to be finished in selected time frame with the use of limited financial resources by which it was difficult for the researcher to manage time and fund. The findings of the research would have been more extensive if more time and resources were provided. In spite of the limitations, the researcher has endeavoured their possible effort to generate appropriate and wider findings on the subject matter to accomplish the pre-set aims and objectives of this research study within the given timeframe.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS

To analyse the impact of technological innovation in the health service delivery in the case of NHS UK, an online survey was conducted among 60 participants that comprise of NHS Staff (service provider) and patients (service user). To find out the perspective and view from the side of both the service user and service provider and to make extensive findings with the help of primary source of data, an online survey was conducted. The online survey was conducted with the help of online portal, Kwiksurveys. For the online survey, a fully structured questionnaire was prepared to base on the aims and objectives of the research. The survey questionnaire consists of three section, section A consist of three questions which were related to the profile of the respondents, section B contains 6 questions that were to be a answered by the NHS staffs (service provider) and section C comprise of 4 questions that were to be answered by the e patients (service user) of NHS UK. The participants for the survey were chosen through the purposive sampling technique. The link to the online survey was sent to the respective participants by email, which was thoroughly filled up them. A total of 31 service user and 29- service provider had participated in the online survey. The results of the online survey have been presented in the consequent section with the help of table and diagram along with brief analysis.

4.1.1 GENDER OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Gender

	Male	Female	Other	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	28 (47%)	31 (52%)	1 (2%)	13.49	60

Figure 1: Gender of participants

Gender was included for knowing about the representation of gender in the survey. In the online survey of total 60 participants took part. The above figure shows that out of 60, 31 (52%) are female, 28 (47%) are male, and 1 (2%) is of another gender. The result shows that there was a slightly high representation of the women in the survey, by which it might be assumed that majority of women, were interested in the topic of technological innovation.

4.1.2 AGE GROUP OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Age Group

	18-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	Above 50	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	4 (7%)	18 (30%)	22 (37%)	10 (17%)	6 (10%)	6.93	60

Figure 2: Age group of participants

The above diagram and table depict the age group of the participants of the survey. In the survey, the majority of the respondents were from the age group 30 to 40 (37%) whereas the least were from the age group of 18-20 (7%). Likewise, 30 % were from the 20 to 30 age group followed by 17% from 40 to 50 age group and 10 % from above 50 ages. The figure above shows that majority of the representation is from active age group, i.e. from 20 to 40.

4.1.3 BACKGROUND OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Background

	Service provider	Service User	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	29 (48%)	31 (52%)	1	60

Figure 3: Background of participants

As this survey was conducted upon both the service provider (NHS staff) and a service user (patients), the portion of the background of the participants was included to know about the how many of the participants were service user and how many were a service provider. The above figure exhibits that 31 (52%) are service user while 29 (48%) are a service provider. There is an only slight change in the number of the participants, equal service user and service provider took part in the online survey.

QUESTIONS TO THE NHS STAFFS

4.1.4 WORKING YEAR

From how long are you working at NHS hospital?

	0-2 year	2-4 year	4-6 year	Above 6 year	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	5 (17%)	11 (38%)	6 (21%)	7 (24%)	2.28	29

Figure 4: Working year

The question about a working year was included to know about, from how old or new staffs, the data and information were collected. Out of 60 participants, 29 are the staffs of NHS. The above diagram depicts mixed results. Slight high percent of staff (38%) were working in NHS from 2 to 4 years while the minimum 17% of the participant staff were working from past two years. Likewise, 24% above were working for more than six years while 21% were working from 4 to six years. The above diagram shows data were collected from both the new and old staffs of NHS; it also demonstrates that many of staffs are working from many years at NHS UK by which it could be known that NHS is a good employer.

4.1.5 PREFERENCE ABOUT TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS

Do you prefer technological innovations in health service system?

	YES	NO	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	25 (86%)	4 (14%)	10.5	29

Figure 5: Preference about technology innovation

In response to the question of their preference about the technological innovations in health service system, 86% of the participants replied positively while 14% replied that they don't prefer technological innovation at their workplace. The figure above depicts that majority of the staffs of NHS UK liked the technological innovations in the health sector which could be due to the development, ease and convenience that technological innovation brought in the entire health sector.

4.1.6 AGREEABLENESS ABOUT TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION’S HELP TO PROVIDE EFFECTIVE HEALTH SERVICE

Technological innovations has helped you to provide effective health service to the NHS’s service users. Agree or Not?

	Agree	Strongly agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	13 (45%)	8 (28%)	3 (10%)	2 (7%)	3 (10%)	4.17	29

Figure 6: agreeableness about technological innovation’s help to provide effective health service

To know about the effectiveness of technological innovation, this question about the agreeableness on the statement that technological innovations have helped you to provide effective health service to NHS service user was asked. The above diagram exhibits that majority of the NHS staff (46%) agreed to the statement, 28 % strongly agreed with it while 10 % strongly oppose it, only 7% disagree and the remaining 10 % were neutral on this question. This connotes that technological innovation has helped the NHS staffs to deliver effective health service to the service users.

4.1.7 IMPACTS OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS ON HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY

What are the impacts of technological innovations on health service delivery at NHS UK?

	● Easy and fast diagnosis and treatment	● Enhanced quality and standard	● Increased efficiency	● Better communication within and outside	● Better research and development	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	9 (31%)	7 (24%)	4 (14%)	4 (14%)	5 (17%)	1.94	29

Figure 7: Impacts of Technology innovation

To find out the impact of technological innovation on the health service delivery at NHS the staffs of NHS were asked about the kind of impact. To this question, total participants staff has responded. The above diagram shows that 31% of the participants replied that technological innovation has impacted on the easy and fast diagnosis and treatment while 24% goes with enhanced quality and standard. On the other hand, 17% thinks that technological innovation has results in better research and development and equal 14% replied increase efficiency and better communication within and outside. The findings show that technological innovations have brought various fruitful impacts on the health care delivery at NHS UK.

4.1.8 CHALLENGES FOR TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN HEALTH SECTOR

What are the challenges for technological innovations in health sector of UK?

	High Cost	Competition	Health care regulatory	Initial implementation problem	Lack of expertise	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	6 (21%)	4 (14%)	4 (14%)	10 (34%)	5 (17%)	2.23	29

Figure 8: Challenges for Technology innovation

The last question to the service provider participants was about the challenges for technological innovations in the health sector of UK. The above diagram shows that the highest, 34% regards initial implementation problem as the major challenges for technological innovations in the health sector. Likewise, 21% considers high cost as the challenge, for 17% its lack of expertise and for equal 14 %, it is competition and health care regulatory.

QUESTIONS TO THE SERVICE USER

4.1.9 RATING OF NHS HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY

How would you rate NHS health service delivery?

	● Good	● Very Good	● Average	● Poor	● Very Poor	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	11 (35%)	9 (29%)	8 (26%)	1 (3%)	2 (6%)	3.97	31

Figure 9: Ratings of NHS Health service Delivery

Out of 60 participants, 31 were the service users (Patients) of NHS. The first question to the service user was about NHS service delivery. The above diagram exhibits that 39 % of the participant service user rated NHS health service delivery as good while 29% reinforced it by providing a very good rating. On the other hand, 28% rated average, 3% rated poor, and 6% rated very poorly. The finding shows a majority of the service user is happy with the health service delivery of NHS UK.

4.1.10 USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN HEALTH SERVICE

Does the hospital you visits make use of technological innovations in health service?

	Yes	NO	Sometimes	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	22 (73%)	1 (3%)	7 (23%)	8.83	30

Figure 10: Use of technology innovation

To know about the use of technological innovations in hospitals of NHS, the NHS service user was about the technological innovations in the hospital they visit. The above diagram shows that almost every NHS hospitals make use of technological innovations at their hospital as only 3% have replied “No” to the question, 73 % have replied “Yes” and 23% have replied “sometimes”. In this question only 30 responses are collected, one of the participants might not have answered this question.

4.1.11 IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS ON HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY

What impact technological innovations have made in health service delivery at NHS UK?

	● Positive Impact	● Negative Impact	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	22 (71%)	9 (29%)	6.5	31

Figure 11: Impact of technological innovation on health service delivery

Likewise, to know the perspective of service user regarding technological innovations, this question was also included in this section. 71% of the participants thought that technological innovation has a positive impact on the health service delivery in the UK while 29% thought it is having a negative impact. Basing on above diagram, it can be said that technological innovation has a positive impact on health care delivery at NHS UK as only a few agree with negative impact.

4.1.12 IMPROVING QUALITY OF HEALTH SERVICE

How health sectors in UK can improve their quality of service?

	● Use of technological innovations	● Skilled health professionals	● Developing communication channel	● Providing patient centric service	Standard Deviation	Responses
All Data	10 (32%)	7 (23%)	7 (23%)	7 (23%)	1.3	31

Figure 12: Improving quality of health service

In the response on how health sector in the UK can improve their quality of service the highest 32% replied it could be by the use of technological innovation while equal 23% regards skilled health professional, providing patient centric service and developing communication channel as the means to enhance the quality of health service in the UK.

4.2 DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

This study tends to analyse the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery of NHS UK. For that, various literary sources in regards to the subject matter were reviewed and analysed with the purpose to unfold different dimension related to technological innovation and its impact on health service delivery. The findings derived from the literature review has already been synthesised in the earlier section by the construction of conceptual framework. Similarly, for the collection of the primary source of data related to the subject matter, an online survey was conducted among the 60 respondents who were a mix of both the service user and service

provider of NHS UK. A fully structured questionnaire that consists of the separate questions for the service user (NHS patients) and service provider (NHS Staff) was used in the online survey for gathering first-hand data and information regarding the subject matter. In total, 29 service provider and the 31-service user had participated in the online survey. In the survey questionnaire, five question was to be answered only the service provider, four question was to be answered only by the service user, and three questions was for both of them. The finding of the survey indicates that technological innovations are making a positive impact on the health service delivery in NHS UK along with the easy and fast diagnosis and treatment, enhanced quality and standard and better research and development (Chang *et al.*, 2012). Likewise, some of the respondents have considered increased efficiency and better communication to be the impact of technological innovations while very few have them also have stated that technological innovations have brought negative impact in health service delivery. With these finding, the study has fulfilled the main aim and objectives and has answered the major research question of this study to explore the impact of technological innovation in the health service delivery at NHS UK. In the survey, there was remarkable representation from all gender and various age groups ranging from 18 to above 50 years. The diversity in gender and age group has helped to ensure the findings to be more wide and relevant. From the survey, it is found that NHS has a mixture of both the old and new staffs; some of the staffs are working there only from past two years while others are working there for six years and above. The presence of staffs working for 4 to 6 years and above six years denotes that NHS is good at retaining their staffs. Likewise, from the survey, it has been found that majority of NHS staffs prefer technological innovation to be employed in their health service system which shows the positive aspects that technological innovations by which the staffs want technological innovations to be incorporated into their health care system (Rodgers, 2008). Similarly, it has been found that technological innovations have helped the service user in providing effective healthcare service to the service user as the majority of respondent show agreement in it and very few have shown disagreement with it (Boyle *et al.*, 2011). This finding reveals the positive impact of technological innovation as it has helped for delivering effective health care service to the service user.

Similarly, the findings derived from the study has depicted that challenges regarding technological innovations are mainly the initial implementation problem, lack of technical expertise and high cost. However few of the respondents have also considered competition and

health care regulations to be a hindrance for technological innovations. This finding has answered another research question which was about the challenges for technological innovations in the health sector. Furthermore, the majority of the respondents (service user) have rated NHS health service delivery as good, very good and average while hardly few have rated it poor and very poor. These findings reveal the quality, standard and likelihood of service user towards NHS. Likewise, from the survey it has been found that the almost all of the hospitals of NHS makes use of technological innovation in the health service although some of them use it sometimes only as high number of respondent have confirmed it with very few denying it, with this it is known that hospitals of NHS have incorporated technological innovation in their health care service (Deloitte, 2015). By this finding, another objective of this study to explore the technological innovations employed in NHS UK has been fulfilled. Moreover, the survey reveals that the quality of health care service could be improved by the use of technological innovation, skilled health care professional, developing communication channel and providing patient centric service (Ceschin and Gaziulusoy, 2016). By this finding, the last objectives of this study to find out the ways to improve the quality of health care service in UK and NHS have been fulfilled.

In addition to this, the findings from the literature review needed to be discussed briefly. A wide range of literary sources were reviewed to explore wider findings on the subject matter. The major findings of the literature review depict that technological innovations have an impact on the health service delivery of NHS UK. From the literature review, it is found that technological innovation has been effective tools for growth, advancement and development of overall health sector and health sector of UK and NHS are making its proper applications (Chen *et al.*, 2014). Likewise, the literature review has depicted the challenges for technological innovations like switching cost, lack of skilled workforce, adaptation and implementation problem. It is found that there has been rapid development in technological innovations. However, not all of the health care organisations can implement and adopt it in an effective manner. Furthermore, the findings of the literature review revealed that there had been positive impacts like enhanced health service quality, increased efficiency, reduction of medical error, improved information technology and others to health service delivery by the technological innovations (Adams *et al.*, 2016). However, some of the negative impacts like costly for the service user and technical errors have been found. Further, it has been found that for enhancing the quality of health care communications, leadership approach, organisational culture, team development and IT are some

of the means that could be used. On the basis of these findings, it could be said that the findings from the literature review has also contributed in fulfilment of research aim and objectives and has attempted to answer the research questions in regards to this study.

4.3 CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of this research study have been able to analyse the impact of technological innovation in health service delivery basing in the case of NHS UK. From the study, it has been found that technological innovation has positive impact alongside few of the negative impact in the health service delivery at NHS UK. Some of the impacts of technological innovations are easy and fast diagnosis and treatment, better communication, enhanced quality and service, better research and development, reduction in medical error, and other. Similar kind of finding was made by Robert Rudowski, who has conducted a study on the impact of ICT on health care, here the impact of e-health one of the form of technological innovations has been explored. Better quality and safer care, improvements access to health care service, and better medical education are some of the benefits of technological innovations in health care system, and ICT development has been seen as the one of the driver and beneficiary in the health sector. Likewise, parallel kind of finding was made by Chaudhry et al. (2006) who have researched to know the impact of health information technology (HIT) on efficiency, quality and cost of medical care. The major finding of that study was that HIT contributes to improvement in quality, guideline based care, surveillance, monitoring, and reduction of medical errors. Health information technology is also one of the kinds of technological innovations that have been rapidly used by health care organisations by which there has been an improvement in health care delivery with enhancing quality, improved monitoring and minimisation of medical errors (Elvira *et al.*, 1994). The findings of these studies differ to the present study in the term that the present study has explored few of the negatives impacts like adaptation problem, costly for the service user and occasional technical defects.

On the other hand, Ellnae Matos et al. (2013) made differential findings in their study of the impact of new technologies in health care. In that study, the major impact of technological impact was found to be in term of workload. The study found that high technologies reduce workloads by reducing physical strain, providing accurate data about service user and developing

collaborative working environment whereas it also increase workloads in the initial phase of technology, and when there is lack of knowledge about how to work with new technologies, here there has been no mention of the increased efficiency, quality and standard. Likewise, in the study of LTH and KL Ong (2002) has presented a slightly differential findings where it has been found that due to the rapidity in the technological innovations developing nations might not be able to catch up appropriately with the technological innovations and the positive impact of technological innovation outweigh its drawbacks like cost issue (Jamal *et al.*, 2009). Although present research has been able to analyse the impact of technological impact in the developed nations like the UK, this study has not tried to insight on the impact of technological innovations on developing nations.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

NHS is the major public health service provider in the UK that provides quality health care services to its citizen free of cost except some of the additional service (Kim *et al.*, 2016). In the present dissertation, the impact that technological innovations have made in the health service delivery mainly in the case of NHS UK has been explored. In the initial part brief introduction to the whole research study was provided (Romanelli, 2016). This study was carried with the main aim to analyse the impact of technological innovations in the health service delivery in NHS UK, concerning this aim, four objectives were set in the study which has been fulfilled through conducting research. Likewise, four research questions were raised at the initial phase of the study, which has been answered by the help of this research study. To accomplish this research study the researcher has make use different apt methodological tools and techniques and has collected both primary and secondary data to make broader findings on the subject matter (Alam Siddiquee, 2008). Secondary sources of data collected through the process of literature review provide a theoretical basis for this study whereas primary sources of data collected through survey questionnaire methods provide a pragmatic basis to the study. The secondary sources of data were collected from various authentic sources like a research paper, journals, articles, scholar's paper, internet sources and other literary sources with consideration of research ethics. From the review and analysis of literary sources in the literature review, it has been found that technological innovations have mainly positive impacts and few negative impacts as well (Boyle *et al.*, 2011). The major positive impacts are improved efficiency and service, upsurge quality, reduction in medical errors and cost and improved information technology system within health along with overall development and advancement of the health care system. On the other hand, the findings of the literature review has depicts some of the negative impacts like a high cost for the service user and mistakes due to technological defects. Likewise, from the literature review, it was found that there has been a high use of technological innovations in health sectors including NHS UK. The major technological innovations tend to be in medical devices and instruments, ways of diagnosis and treatment and in information technology system (Liddell, A., Adshead, S. and Burgess, 2008). However, some of the challenges like adaptation issues, lack of

skilled professional, switching cost, operational and legal aspects are prominent issues for the technological innovations in the health sector. Likewise, it was found that some of the ways to improve the quality of health care are communications, leadership approach, organisational culture, team development and IT. In overall, the literature review has been able to unfold the impact of technological innovations in health service delivery at NHS UK along with the fulfilment of pre-stated aims and objectives.

For researching effective ways, various methodological tools and techniques were employed in this research study. In term of philosophy positivism, philosophy was applied for making empirical findings by previous findings and collection of factual data and information. Likewise, deductive approach was adopted in this study, which has enabled the researcher to test the validity of theories in regards to the subject matter. The quantitative research method was chosen for the study along with the use of survey questionnaire.

Also this, for the collection of the primary source of data, an online survey with the use of questionnaire was conducted among the 60 participants that consist of both the service provider and service user of NHS UK. The questionnaire was made with regards to the aims and objectives of this study and with motives to seek the answers to the research questions which was fulfilled through the successful completion of the online survey. The findings of the survey depicted that that NHS has been able to establish its good image among the service user as the majority of the service user has rated NHS “good” in term of health service delivery. Likewise, it is found that NHS has made use of technological innovations in their health service delivery and this has supported health professionals to provide effective health service to the service user. However, there are various challenges like initial implementation problem, high cost, and lack of expertise, competition and health care regulation that arises in the way of technological innovations in the health sector of UK. Similarly, the survey has been able to analyse the impact of technological innovations in health service delivery at NHS UK. The majority of the respondents’ thinks that technological innovations have made positive impacts while few of them invoke negative impacts as well. Basing on the findings of the online survey it could be concluded that easy and fast diagnosis and treatment, enhanced quality and standard, better research and development, improved efficiency and better communication within and outside are the noticeable impacts that technological innovations have made in the health service delivery of

UK (Elvira *et al.*, 1994). Moreover, the findings of the survey reveal that the quality of health sectors in the UK could be improved by the use of technological innovations in the health sector, skilled health professionals, providing patient centric service and developing communication challenges.

In overall, this research study has been able to make findings related to technological innovations about health service delivery of NHS UK through exploring the features of health care services in the UK and finding out the technological innovations employed in NHS UK. Similarly, through conducting research, the study has analysed the impact of technological innovations in health service delivery of NHS UK along with finding out the challenges for technological innovations and means to improve the quality of service.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Through this study, it is found that NHS UK is making use of technological innovations in their health care system and it has incorporated efficiency, innovation, development and advancement in their health service delivery. Through the study, the impact of technology innovation in health service delivery of NHS UK has been analysed, and it has been found that NHS is providing effective health services with the use of technological innovations. However, there are few areas where improvements could be made. Below are some of the recommendations with regards to NHS for further improvement and innovations:

- From the present study, it has been found that technological innovation has a positive impact on the health service delivery. It is recommended that NHS should further centralised their technological ventures at core place and developed new and time relevant policies and strategies regarding technological innovation.
- NHS is the major public health service provider in the UK, is responsible for ensuring that quality health service is provided to the people. Thus, it should evaluate its health service quality within its hospital on time-to-time basis; it should check if its hospitals are following and meeting the NHS's standard and guidelines or not. Also, if necessary it should direct them for improvements in quality and standard in health service delivery.

- As NHS is a government funded healthcare organisation, it should work in strong collaboration with the government to employed new technologies in their healthcare system.
- Likewise, it is recommended that NHS UK should evaluate the impact of technological innovations on a regular basis to keep track of what kinds of innovations are bringing what kind of impacts. Through it, NHS will know about the types of technological innovation that are more fruitful to uplift the health service delivery and could focus on such types of innovation.
- From the present, it is found that, although NHS is making use of technological innovations in their health service system, initial implementation is one of the major problems in adoption of technological innovation. For that, NHS should train their employees about new technologies properly and should strictly monitor the initial implementation phase. Further, service user should also be made aware new technologies used and how they could be benefitted by it.
- Similarly, NHS should develop effective communication channel to interact and communicate with the service user and the health professional as communication help in relationship building and improving service quality.
- Moreover, it is recommended that NHS should develop a clear leadership approach and positive organisational culture that promotes technological innovation in their health care service system by which they could deliver more advanced and quality service to the service user.
- Also, further study of similar kind of topic is recommended as only a few studies have been conducted regarding the impact of technological innovation on health service delivery. As this study was time and resource bound which has limited the findings as well, further study on a similar topic will be helpful to make a wide range of findings on the subject matter.

REFERENCE

1. Adams, R., Jeanrenaud, S., Bessant, J., Denyer, D., Overy, P. (2016) Sustainability-oriented Innovation: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*. **18**(2), 180–205.
2. Akenroye, T.O. (2012) Factors Influencing Innovation in Healthcare: A conceptual synthesis. **17**(2).
3. Alam Siddiquee, N. (2008) Service delivery innovations and governance: the Malaysian experience. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*. **2**(3), 194–213.
4. Angst, C.M. (2007) Information technology and its transformational effect on the health care industry.
5. Baek, J.S., Meroni, A., Manzini, E. (2015) A socio-technical approach to design for community resilience: A framework for analysis and design goal forming. *Design Studies*. **40**, 60–84.
6. Bhaskar, R. (2008) On the Ontological Status of Ideas. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*. **27**(2–3), 139–147.
7. Boyle, S., Mckee, M., Allin, S., Krasnik, A., Marchildon, G., Maynard, A., Van De Ven, W.P.M.M. (2011) *Health Systems in Transition*. . **13**(1).
8. Bryman, A. (2015a) *Business Research Methods*. 3rd editio. OUP Oxford.
9. Bryman, A. (2015b) *Social Research Methods*. OUP Oxford.
10. Ceschin, F., Gaziulusoy, I. (2016) Evolution of design for sustainability: From product design to design for system innovations and transitions. *Design Studies*. **47**, 118–163.
11. Chang, J., Peysakhovich, F., Wang, W., Zhu, J. (2012) *The UK Health Care System*.
12. Chen, S.-H., Wen, P.-C., Yang, C.-K. (2014) Business concepts of systemic service innovations in e-Healthcare. *Technovation*. **34**(9), 513–524.

13. Cohen, C.S. (2014) No magic bullets: a mixed methods case study to evaluate the implementation of an e-health system designed to support evidence-based practice in primary and community care settings.
14. Cohen, L., Manion, L., Morrison, K. (2011) *Research Methods in Education*. 7 edition. Routledge.
15. Creswell, J.W. (2014) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
16. Creswell, J.W., Clark, V.L.P. (2011) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. 2nd editio. SAGE Publications.
17. Dawson, D.C. (2013) *Advanced Research Methods: A Practical Guide for Social Research Projects (How to)*. How To Books.
18. Deloitte (2015) *Connected Health: How digital technology is transforming health and social care.* , 38.
19. Duncan, A.K., Breslin, M.A. (2009) Innovating health care delivery: the design of health services V. Kumar, ed. *Journal of Business Strategy*. **30**(2/3), 13–20.
20. Easton, G. (2010) Critical realism in case study research. *Industrial Marketing Management*. **39**(1), 118–128.
21. Elke Jakubowski, D., Reinhard Busse, D., Kahan, J., Kanavos, P., Bastida-Lopez, J., Mossialos, E., Wiley, M., Sassi, F. (1998) *Health Care Systems In The Eu A Comparative Study*.
22. Ericsson, S. (2014) Barriers of developing and implementing IT-innovation in healthcare A process study of challenges in eHealth development.
23. Georgiadis, G., Mehl, A. (2016) Financial globalisation and monetary policy effectiveness. *Journal of International Economics*. **103**, 200–212.

24. Graziano, A.M., Raulin, M.L. (2012) *Research methods + mysearchlab with etext: a process of inquiry*. Prentice Hall.
25. Hussain, M.K. (2015) *A Conceptual Foresight Model To Investigate The Adoption Of Radio Frequency Identification Technology In The English National Health Service*.
26. Jamal, A., Mckenzie, K., Clark, M. (2009) The impact of health information technology on the quality of medical and health care: a systematic review. *HEALTH INFORMATION MANAGEMENT JOURNAL*. **38**(3), 1833–3583.
27. Khan, M., Khan, M.A. (2009) How technological innovations extend services outreach to customers. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. **21**(5), 509–522.
28. Kim, R.H., Gaukler, G.M., Lee, C.W. (2016) Improving healthcare quality: A technological and managerial innovation perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. **113**, 373–378.
29. Kruk, M.E., Kujawski, S., Moyer, C.A., Adanu, R.M., Afsana, K., Cohen, J., Glassman, A., Labrique, A., Reddy, K.S., Yamey, G. (2016) Next generation maternal health: external shocks and health-system innovations. *The Lancet*. **388**(10057), 2296–2306.
30. Kumar, R. (2014) *Research Methodology: A Step-by-Step Guide for Beginners*. 4th Revise. SAGE Publications Ltd.
31. Liddell, A., Adshead, S. and Burgess, E. (2008) *Technology in the NHS transforming the patient's experience of care*.
32. Manager, L., Services, Ausinfo (1920) *International approaches to funding health care Occasional Papers: Health Financing Series Volume 5*. , 642–41581.
33. Matthews, D.B., Ross, L. (2010) *Research Methods: A Practical Guide for the Social Sciences*. 01 edition. Longman.

34. Merali, F. (2014) Managing within the challenges & tensions facing the 21 st Century UK NHS Managers: NHS Managers' perceptions of their public image & the implications for their self and work identity.
35. Nazali Mohd Noor, M., Pitt, M. (2009) A critical review on innovation in facilities management service delivery. *Facilities*. **27**(5/6), 211–228.
36. Omachonu, V.K., Einspruch, N.G. (2010) Innovation in Healthcare Delivery Systems: A Conceptual Framework. . 15(151).
37. Quality Commission, C. (2015) The state of health care and adult social care in England 2015/16.
38. Ranta, P. (2010) Information and Communications Technology in Health Care Economics Master's thesis.
39. Rodgers, S. (2008) Technological innovation supporting different food production philosophies in the food service sectors. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. **20**(1), 19–34.
40. Romanelli, M. (2016a) New Technologies for Sustainable Health Care. In Springer, Cham, pp. 674–682.
41. Romanelli, M. (2016b) New Technologies for Sustainable Health Care. , 674–682.
42. Saunders, M.N.K., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A. (2015) *Research Methods for Business Students*. Trans-Atlantic Publications, Inc.
43. Sheingold, B.H., Hahn, J.A. (2014) The history of healthcare quality: The first 100 years 1860–1960. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*. 1, 18–22.
44. TESCO (2014) *Tesco Corporation Code of Business Conduct and Ethics*.
45. Thomas, G. (2013) *How to Do Your Research Project: A Guide for Students in Education and Applied Social Sciences*. SAGE Publications Ltd.

46. Trochim, W., Donnelly, J.P., Arora, K. (2015) *Research Methods: The Essential Knowledge Base*. Cengage Learning.
47. Van Egmond-de Wilde de Ligny, E.L.C., Mohammadi, M. (2011) Innovations in domotics: fulfilling potential or hampered by prevailing technological regime? J. E. Tookey, ed. *Construction Innovation*. **11**(4), 470–492.
48. Wa, E., Rt, O., Ferlie, E.B., Shortell, S.M. (2001) Improving the Quality of Health Care in the United Kingdom and the United States: A Framework for Change. *The Milbank Quarterly*. **79**(2).
49. Walliman, N. (2015) *Research Methods: The Basics*. Routledge.
50. Weber, K.M., Heller-Schuh, B., Godoe, H., Roeste, R. (2014) ICT-enabled system innovations in public services: Experiences from intelligent transport systems. *Telecommunications Policy*. **38**(5), 539–557.
51. White, T.L., McBurney, D.H. (2012) *Research Methods*. Cengage Learning.
52. Windrum, P., Schartinger, D., Rubalcaba, L., Gallouj, F., Toivonen, M. (2016) The co-creation of multi-agent social innovations. *European Journal of Innovation Management*. **19**(2), 150–166

APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

APPENDIX 2: LINK OF THE ONLINE SURVEY

<https://kwiksurveys.com/s/3fZp2wwd#/0>

APPENDIX 3: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION ON HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY

WITH THE PARTICIPATION IN THIS RESEARCH, YOU AGREE THAT:

- PARTICIPANTS WERE VOLUNTARY TO PARTICIPATE IN THE RESEARCH
- THERE WONT BE ANY RISK OR HARM TO THE PARTICIPANTS
- CONFIDENTIALITY WILL BE MAINTAINED IN THE PARTICIPANTS PERSONAL INFORMATION
- WE PRESUME THAT THE CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH IS UNDERSTOOD BY THE PARTICIPANTS

QUESTION 1 TO 3 ARE THE PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

QUESTION 4 TO 8 ARE THE QUESTIONS TO THE NHS STAFFS

QUESTION 9 TO 12 ARE THE QUESTIONS TO THE SERVICE USERS

1*) Gender

<input type="radio"/> A Male	<input type="radio"/> B Female	<input type="radio"/> C Other
------------------------------	--------------------------------	-------------------------------

2*) Age Group

<input type="radio"/> A 18-20	<input type="radio"/> B 20-30	<input type="radio"/> C 30-40
<input type="radio"/> D 40-50	<input type="radio"/> E Above 50	

3*) Background

<input type="radio"/> A Service provider	<input type="radio"/> B Service User
--	--------------------------------------

4) From how long are you working at NHS hospital?

A 0-2 year

B 2-4 year

C 4-6 year

D Above 6 year

5) Do you prefer technological innovations in health service system?

A YES

B NO

6) Technological innovations has helped you to provide effective health service to the NHS's service users. Agree or Not?

A Agree

B Strongly agree

C Neutral

D Disagree

E Strongly Disagree

7) What are the impacts of technological innovations on health service delivery at NHS UK?

A Easy and fast diagnosis and treatment

B Enhanced quality and standard

C Increased efficiency

D Better communication within and outside

E Better research and development

8) What are the challenges for technological innovations in health sector of UK?

A High Cost

B Competition

C Health care regulatory

D Initial implementation problem

E Lack of expertise

9) How would you rate NHS health service delivery?

A	Good	B	Very Good	C	Average
D	Poor	E	Very Poor		

10) Does the hospital you visits make use of technological innovations in health service?

A	Yes	B	NO	C	Sometimes
---	-----	---	----	---	-----------

11) What impact technological innovations have made in health service delivery at NHS UK?

A	Positive Impact	B	Negative Impact
---	-----------------	---	-----------------

12) How health sectors in UK can improve their quality of service?

A	Use of technological innovations	B	Skilled health professionals	C	Developing communication channel
D	Providing patient centric service				

THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION

APPENDIX 4 PARTICIPATION INFORMATION FORM

London School
of Marketing

University of
Northampton

Working in partnership with

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET (PIS)

Section A: The Research Project

1. Title of project

Analyzing the Impact of Technological Innovation on Health Service Delivery: A Case Study of NH

2. Research Summary.

Technology has been an important part of the health service delivery system in NHS. so, the research will be based on the quantitative information selected from the participation explore on the importance of the technology innovation.

3. Objective of the Research:

Postgraduate degree at University of Northampton

4. Name of your Supervisor (*student research only*).

Asanthi kodituwakku

5. Reason for Participation:

NHS is a largest health organisation in UK and it has major impact on the people living there, also there has been rapid development of technology in few years so the area is worth exploration

6. How many participants will be involved in the research?

there will be 60-80 participants involved in the research

7. Can I refuse to take part?

Yes

No

8. Has the study got ethical approval?

The research has got the ethical approval fro university of northampton

9. Has the organisation where you are carrying out the research given permission?

the permission wasn't required in case of this research

10. Source of funding for the research, if applicable.

there is no funding provided for the project

11. What will happen to the results of the study?

the result of the study will be solely used for the research only

12. Contact for further information (*Student e-mail address*)

dr.brahmi@hotmail.com

Section B: Your Participation in the Research Project

1. What will I be asked to do?

you will be provided the link to the survey where a list of questions will be provided.

2. Will my participation in the study be kept confidential?

yes, all the information of the participants be kept confidential

3. Whether I can withdraw at any time, and how.

the participant can withdraw at any moment

4. What will happen to any information/data/samples that are collected from you?

The data will be stored safely and after the completion of the research the data will be destroyed.

5. Contact details for complaints.

dr.brahmi@hotmail.com